

HMM-Based POS Tagging in Hindi: A Viterbi Algorithm and Smoothing Analysis

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ABSTRACT:

Part-of-speech (POS) tagging plays a pivotal role in Natural Language Processing, providing valuable metadata for various downstream tasks such as syntactic parsing, information retrieval, sentiment analysis, machine translation, named entity recognition, and speech recognition. While significant progress has been made in POS tagging for English, the landscape for Hindi remains relatively underexplored. Limited availability of tagged datasets poses a unique challenge in training accurate POS taggers for Hindi. In this study, we aim to explore this gap by training a Hidden Markov Model (HMM) and evaluating its performance using the Viterbi algorithm. We specifically focus on assessing the model's ability to handle unseen or unknown words, crucial for real-world applications, and evaluate the impact of smoothing techniques too. Our results show that the non-smoothed model achieves higher overall accuracy and significantly better performance on unknown words compared to the smoothed version. Interestingly, precision and recall across POS tags remain consistent between both models, suggesting comparable effectiveness in tagging individual categories despite differences in overall performance.

Keywords: POS Tagging, HMM, Viterbi, Laplace Smoothing.

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INTRODUCTION

Despite the pivotal role of Part-of-Speech (POS) tagging in Natural Language Processing (NLP), its application in languages like Hindi remains relatively underexplored. While significant progress has been made in POS tagging for English, adapting these advancements to languages with distinct linguistic characteristics poses unique challenges. Hindi, being a widely spoken language globally, presents a prime example of such challenges.

Initial attempts were made to develop POS taggers using morphological rules [17] due to the unavailability of sufficiently large corpora. Shrivastava et al. utilized Stemmer, a morphological analyzer for Hindi, to build a rule-based POS tagger [17]. Similarly, Ranjan et al. [1] described a POS tagger based on lexical sequence constraints in Hindi using morphological analyzer rules [17].

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Rao [2] demonstrated the improvement of accuracy for out of vocabulary words in Hindi through suffix- based POS tagging and found TnT tagger to perform best for Hindi, Bengali, and Telugu. Varma et al. [3] developed a language-independent POS tagger based on HMM, tested for English and Hindi [17].

Moreover, the study by Dutta et al. [4] proposes an Intelligent POS tagger for Hindi, leveraging both VITERBI and K-Nearest Neighbour algorithms [17]. Their approach aims to enhance accuracy, especially in scenarios involving unknown words, which are prevalent in Indian languages due to diverse vocabulary and contextual usage. K-means clustering to categorize words with similar meanings has been used in various NLP tasks [5]. By combining Laplace smoothing and KNN, the proposed algorithm demonstrates improved performance compared to traditional methods like Viterbi.

The Viterbi algorithm is a foundational dynamic programming technique used to determine the most probable sequence of hidden states in a Hidden Markov Model (HMM), given a sequence of observed events [12]. Originally introduced by Andrew Viterbi in the 1960s [6], the algorithm has become a standard tool in fields such as speech recognition, bioinformatics, and natural language processing.

In the context of part-of-speech (POS) tagging, a widely adopted approach involves modeling the POS tags as the hidden states of an HMM, with the observed sequence being the words in a sentence. The model is trained to learn transition probabilities (the likelihood of moving from one POS tag to another) and emission probabilities (the likelihood of a word being generated from a given POS tag). After training, these probabilities form the basis of a transition-emission matrix, over which the Viterbi algorithm efficiently computes the most likely sequence of tags for a given sentence. Using a trigram HMM POS tagger and the Viterbi algorithm for decoding, Kumawat et al. reported an average accuracy of 95.45% across tourism, health, and general sentence categories [7]. This finding underscores our decision to adopt this approach as the foundation for our work.

As highlighted by Devashish Dutta et al. [4], it is crucial for a POS tagging system to effectively handle unknown or out-of-vocabulary (OOV) words, especially in low-resource languages like Hindi. The performance of Hidden Markov Models (HMMs) improves with larger training corpora, as these reduce the frequency of unseen words. Traditional techniques such as Laplace smoothing, which are effective in other contexts, have not produced satisfactory results for Hindi POS Tagging. To address this, our study investigates the ability of HMM-based POS taggers to generalize unknown words. We evaluated models trained on the Universal Dependencies Hindi dataset and compared them to models trained on additional corpora. This provided insights into the robustness of stochastic HMMs in handling unknown words challenges. Also, Machine learning techniques have shown broad applicability across domains, from multimedia content analysis [8] to linguistic modeling, supporting the effectiveness of systematic evaluation in data-driven tasks. In domains with limited annotated data, synthetic data generation has been shown to improve model performance [9]. Motivated by this, we explore smoothing and data generation techniques for improving HMM-based POS tagging in Hindi.

Hindi's syntactic flexibility, which permits relatively free word order in sentences, adds a layer of complexity to POS tagging. Hindi requires sophisticated analysis of word relationships and sentence structure to accurately assign POS tags. Addressing these challenges is essential for enabling various downstream NLP tasks in Hindi, ranging from syntactic parsing to sentiment analysis and machine translation. However, the limited availability of tagged datasets for Hindi poses a significant obstacle in training accurate POS taggers. Therefore, this study aims to bridge this gap by leveraging a Hidden Markov Model (HMM) and evaluating its performance using the Viterbi algorithm.

Our study addresses the following research questions:

- **RQ1:** How effective is the Viterbi algorithm in decoding POS tags within a Hidden Markov Model trained on the Universal Dependencies dataset?
- **RQ2:** How does the stochastic HMM model perform when tested with unknown words?

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This section outlines the approach employed to build a Part-of-Speech (POS) tagger using a Hidden Markov Model (HMM). We describe the process of estimating emission and transition probabilities, implementing the Viterbi algorithm for decoding, and handling unknown words through synthetic generation. Additionally, we apply Laplace smoothing to improve the model's robustness and generalization when encountering uncommon or unseen tag sequences.

To begin constructing our Hidden Markov Model (HMM), we'll first select a dataset. We've opted for the Universal Dependencies dataset [10], which offers around 20,000 tagged Hindi sentences. Universal Dependencies (UD) serves as a framework for consistent grammar annotation, encompassing parts of speech, morphological features, and syntactic dependencies across diverse human languages. With over 500 contributors, UD has generated over 200 treebanks in over 100 languages, making it a rich resource for linguistic analysis.

In its raw form, the Universal Dependencies data is presented as a treebank, containing more information than necessary for our task, as we're solely interested in part-of-speech tags.

```
# sent_id = train-s1
# text = यह एशिया की सबसे बड़ी मस्जिदों में से एक है ।
1 यह यह DET-DEM Case=Nom|Number=Sing|Person=3|PronType=Dem 2 det _ ChunkId=NP|ChunkType=child
2 एशिया एशिया PROP-NNP Case=Acc|Gender=Masc|Number=Sing|Person=3 6 nmod _ Vib=0_का|
3 की का ADP-PSP AdpType=Post|Case=Acc|Gender=Fem|Number=Plur 2 case _ ChunkId=NP|ChunkType=child
4 सबसे सबसे ADV-INTF AdvType=Deg 5 advmod _ AltTag=avy-ADV|ChunkId=NP2|ChunkType=child
5 बड़ी बड़ा ADJ-JJ Case=Acc|Gender=Fem|Number=Plur 6 amod _ ChunkId=NP2|ChunkType=child
6 मस्जिदों मस्जिद NOUN-NN Case=Acc|Gender=Fem|Number=Plur|Person=3 9 nmod _ Vib=0_में
7 में में ADP-PSP AdpType=Post 6 case _ ChunkId=NP2|ChunkType=child|Translit=meñ
8 से से ADP-PSP AdpType=Post 6 case _ ChunkId=NP2|ChunkType=child|Translit=se
9 एक एक NUM-QC NumType=Card 0 root _ ChunkId=NP3|ChunkType=head|Translit=eka
10 है है AUX-VM Mood=Ind|Number=Sing|Person=3|Tense=Pres|VerbForm=Fin|Voice=Act 9 cop _ ChunkId=
11 । । PUNCT-SYM 9 punct _ ChunkId=BLK|ChunkType=head|Translit=.
```

Figure 1. Universal Dependencies Hindi treebank in CoNLL-U format

To refine the dataset for our purposes, we'll pre-process it. This involves parsing the raw Universal Dependencies dataset into a more suitable format, wherein each word in a sentence is followed by a slash (/) and its corresponding part-of-speech tag. This streamlined format will facilitate the creation of our Hidden Markov Model.

```
इस/PRON नवाब/NOUN शाहजहन/PROP-NN न/ADP बनवाया/VERB था/AUX ।/PUNCT
इसका/PRON प्रवेश/NOUN द्वार/NOUN दो/NUM मंजिला/ADJ है/AUX ।/PUNCT
```

Figure 2. Dataset After Pre-Processing

Hidden Markov Model

To train the Hidden Markov Model (HMM), we must generate emission and transition bigram probabilities. In essence, emission probability for a given word and tag pair is given by [11] and [18]:

$$P(\text{word} | \text{tag}) = \frac{\text{Count}(\text{word}, \text{tag})}{\text{Count}(\text{tag})} \quad (1)$$

Where: P (word | tag): Probability of observing a given word tag, Count (word, tag): Word and tag bigram count, Count (tag): Total count of occurrences of the POS tag.

Pseudocode to generate emission count is given below:

- 1: Initialize an empty dictionary called *emission_count*.
- 2: for each sentence in the training data:
- 3: for each word_n_tag in sentence:
- 4: If word_n_tag in *emission_count*:
- 5: Increment its count by 1
- 6: else:
- 7: Set its count to 1
- 8: **end if**
- 9: **end for**
- 10: **end for**

Also, the pseudocode to calculate emission probability is given below:

- 1: Initialize an empty dictionary called *emission_probability*.
- 2: For word_tag_pair in *emission_count*:
- 3: Set variable *tag* equals to *extract_tag_from_word_tag_pair(word_tag_pair)*
- 4: Set *emission_probability[word_tag_pair]* equals to *emission_count[word_tag_pair] / tag_count[tag]*
- 5: **end for**

Figure 3. Transition and Emission Probabilities in a Hidden Markov Model

Similarly, to get transition probabilities we will follow the following formula [11] and [19]:

$$P(t_i | t_{i-1}) = \frac{C(t_{i-1}, t_i)}{C(t_{i-1})} \quad (2)$$

Where: $P(t_i | t_{i-1})$ is the probability of tag t_i occurring after tag t_{i-1} , $C(t_{i-1}, t_i)$ is the count of the bigram (tag t_{i-1} , tag t_i) in the training corpus, $C(t_{i-1})$ is the count of tag t_{i-1} occurring overall in the training corpus.

HMM weights

start->SYM : 0.00003167162855514030531449927155

SYM->NNP : 0.3781048758049678012879484821

TRANSITION

NNP->NNP : 0.3613162179559998485364837745

साथ & RDP : 0.001430615164520743919885550787

पेरिस & NNP : 0.0002834065466912285673799064758

EMISSION

अतीत & NN : 0.00009232331625351982643216544338

साक्षात्कार & NN : 0.0001230977550046931019095539245

कर & VM:0.02719412888308032572634965316

Figure 4. Transition and Emission Probabilities Weights by Example

Viterbi Algorithm

The Viterbi algorithm is a dynamic programming approach used to find the most probable sequence of hidden states in a Hidden Markov Model (HMM), given a sequence of observations [12]. It is particularly useful in part-of-speech tagging, where the hidden states represent the part-of-speech tags, and the observations are the words in a sentence.

The algorithm works by recursively calculating the probability of the most probable path to each state at each time step, given the previous states. It then selects the state with the highest probability at each time step to construct the most probable sequence of states.

A Hidden Markov Model is defined by [13] and [20]:

$$P(y, x) = P_s(y_1) P_e(x_1 | y_1) \left[\prod_{i=2}^n P_t(y_i | y_{i-1}) P_e(x_i | y_i) \right] P_t(\text{Stop} | y_n)$$

Let U denote the set of tags (to avoid collision with T defined above) and let n be the length of a sentence under consideration [20]. Assume that tags and words are both indexed, so that both words and tags can be represented as integers [20]. The set of tags should contain a STOP token [20]. When doing English tagging, correctly accounting for STOP at the end doesn't actually change the results that much since most sentences end in punctuation; however, it's necessary to make the model a correct probabilistic model (sums to 1 over all possible tagged sequences) [20].

The Viterbi algorithm is a dynamic programming approach to computing the highest scoring path [20]. At its core is an $n \times |U| - 1$ matrix v , where the matrix excludes the STOP state. $v[i, y]$ stores the log probability so far of the highest probability path ending in y at state i [20].

1: function VITERBI (x, S, T, E), x : sentence of length n , S : initial log probs, T : transition log probs, E : emission log probs

2: Initialize v , a $n \times |U| - 1$ matrix

3: for $y = 1$ to $|U| - 1$ **do** > Handle the initial state

4: $v[1, y] = S[y] + E[y, x_1]$

5: **end for**


```

6: for i = 2 to n do
7: for y = 1 to |U| - 1 do
8:  $v[i, y] = E[y, xi] + \max_{y_{prev}} (T[y_{prev}, y] + v[i-1, y_{prev}])$ 
9: end for
10: end for
11: for y = 1 to |U| - 1 do
12:  $v[n, y] = v[n, y] + T[y, Stop]$ 
13: end for > Handle the final state
14: Best final state =  $v[n, y] + T[y, Stop]$ 
15: To reconstruct the answer: track argmaxes as well (where the max element values come from)
and walk backwards to find the sequence [20].

```

Synthetic Generation of Unseen or Unknown Words

In this experiment, our aim is to assess and contrast the effectiveness of a stochastic Hidden Markov Model (HMM) when faced with unfamiliar words.

Because of a lack of availability of additional datasets to train and test against, we applied random sampling to generate a test and training split of the Universal Dependencies dataset with unknown word representation. First, a random word from the existing dataset vocabulary was designated as an unknown word. Sentences containing this unknown word were assigned to the test set, while those without it were included in the training set.

Laplace Smoothing

To improve model performance when handling unknown words or uncommon tag sequences, Laplace smoothing (also known as add-one smoothing) was applied to the transition probabilities in the Hidden Markov Model. Laplace smoothing is a smoothing technique that helps tackle the problem of zero probability [14, 21]. This method increases extremely low probabilities, including zero values—while slightly reducing very high probabilities. Smoothing not only helps to avoid zero-probability issues but also aims to enhance the overall accuracy and generalization ability of the model [15].

For example, if the transition key is from NN to JJ, the prefix tag is NN, and smoothing ensures that even if NN → JJ did not appear in training, it still gets a small non-zero probability in the transition matrix. The general formula for Laplace smoothing is given below:

$$P_{\text{smoothed}}(x) = \frac{\text{Count}(x) + \alpha}{N + \alpha * V} \quad (3)$$

Where Count(x): Number of times event x is observed, N is the total number of observations, V is the total number of possible unique events (vocabulary size or state size), α is the smoothing parameter (typically $\alpha = 1$ for Laplace smoothing).

Initially, we set alpha to 1 (using add-1 smoothing) as our first approach. However, this strategy is not universally optimal for all datasets and problem scenarios. Therefore, we conducted iterative experiments to determine the most suitable alpha parameter for training.

Evaluation Metrics

In Part-of-Speech (POS) tagging, evaluating the model's performance is crucial to understand how accurately it assigns the correct tags to words. We have used the following evaluation metrics [16] to assess the model's performance.

The overall accuracy measures the proportion of correct predictions made by the model over the total number of predictions. It provides an understanding of how accurate the model is in making correct POS tag predictions.

The known word accuracy calculates the proportion of correct predictions made for known words over the total number of predictions for known words. It helps understand the accuracy of the model when making predictions for words that are already present in the training data.

The unknown word accuracy measures the proportion of correct predictions made for unknown words over the total number of predictions for unknown words. It evaluates the accuracy of the model when making predictions for words that are not present in the training data.

Precision per tag assesses the relevance of retrieved tags by calculating the proportion of correctly classified instances as a specific tag over all instances classified as that tag. It provides a granular evaluation of the model's performance for each POS tag.

Recall per tag measures the proportion of relevant instances retrieved for a specific tag over the total number of instances that belong to that tag in the test set. It offers a granular evaluation of the model's ability to retrieve relevant instances for each POS tag.

RESULTS

To address the research question on the effectiveness of our Hidden Markov Model (HMM) for Part-of-Speech (POS) tagging, we conducted three separate evaluations. Following the methodology detailed earlier, we randomly split the dataset into 80% training data (13313 sentences) and 20% test data (3317 sentences).

Table 1. Accuracies in Each Run

Run	Accuracy (%)	Wrong Predictions	Total Predictions
1	89.43	6952	65778
2	92.35	5026	65696
3	86.61	8816	65848

Table 1 summarizes the accuracy achieved in each run along with the count of wrong predictions and total predictions made.

To assess the model's resilience to handling unknown words, we explored the impact of various emission smoothing parameters (α). Figures 5 and 6 showcase the model's performance across different α values, with 'null' indicating no smoothing.

Observing Figures 5 and 6, an α value of 0.08 emerges as the optimal parameter choice. Hence, for subsequent evaluations, we adopt 0.08 as the emission smoothing parameter. However, when evaluated against the same train-test split with 0.08 as the emission smoothing parameter, the model's performance deteriorated across all metrics due to overfitting. Figure 7 illustrates the model's struggle, particularly evident in both precision and recall metrics for underrepresented data points. Notably, tags with fewer occurrences exhibit nearly negligible results. Also, from Figure 7 and Figure 8, we can observe that the precision and recall values across different POS tags remain relatively consistent between the smoothed and non-smoothed models. This suggests that the model, despite the use of smoothing, is similarly effective in correctly predicting specific tags (precision) and in capturing the actual occurrences of those tags in the data (recall), even though their overall accuracy differs.

This underscores the need for a more adaptive approach to smoothing or managing unknown words.

Figure 5. Overall and Known Word Accuracy with Various Smoothing Parameters (α)

Figure 6. Unknown Word Accuracy with Various Smoothing Parameters (α)

Figure 7. Precision and Recall with Smoothing Parameter (α)

Figure 8. Precision and Recall without Smoothing Parameter (α)

Table 2. Comparison of Model Accuracies

Accuracy	With Smoothing (%)	Without Smoothing (%)
Total Accuracy	89.27	93.61
Accuracy on Unknown Words	60.61	79.48
Accuracy on Known Words	90.48	94.21

Table 2 presents the performance comparison between the models trained with and without smoothing. The results indicate that applying smoothing reduces overall accuracy across all evaluation metrics.

The model without smoothing achieved a total accuracy of 93.61%, outperforming the smoothed version which attained 89.27%. Notably, the accuracy on known words was higher without smoothing (94.21%) compared to the smoothed version (90.48%). Similarly, accuracy on unknown words showed a significant improvement without smoothing, reaching 79.48% as opposed to 60.61% with smoothing. These results suggest that while smoothing is typically used to handle unseen data, in this case, it may have negatively impacted the model's ability to generalize effectively.

CONCLUSION

This study explored the application of Hidden Markov Models (HMMs) for Part-of-Speech (POS) tagging in Hindi, a morphologically rich and syntactically flexible language. By leveraging the Universal Dependencies Hindi dataset, we trained an HMM-based tagger and employed the Viterbi algorithm for decoding. Our investigation focused on the model's ability to generalize to unseen words—an important factor for low-resource languages like Hindi. Surprisingly, the non-smoothed HMM outperformed the smoothed version, particularly in tagging unknown words, suggesting that smoothing techniques like Laplace may dilute essential tag-word associations in such contexts. Nevertheless, both models exhibited comparable precision and recall across individual POS tags, indicating stable category-level performance. Overall, our findings highlight that with appropriate modeling choices, HMMs remain a viable solution for POS tagging in Hindi, especially when dealing with resource constraints.

Despite promising results, our study is subject to several limitations. First, the scope was restricted to bigram HMMs, which may not fully capture long-range dependencies and contextual cues necessary for resolving ambiguous tags in free-word-order languages like Hindi. Second, the Laplace smoothing technique applied may have been too simplistic for effectively handling rare transitions and emissions, suggesting a need for more nuanced methods like Good-Turing or Kneser-Ney smoothing.

Future work can extend this study by exploring more expressive sequence models, such as Conditional Random Fields (CRFs) or deep learning-based architectures like BiLSTM-CRFs, which can inherently handle context better and integrate additional linguistic features. Incorporating

morphological analyzers or subword-level embeddings may further enhance performance, particularly on out-of-vocabulary words. Finally, building larger annotated corpora and adapting semi-supervised learning or transfer learning from high-resource languages can help overcome data scarcity challenges in Hindi POS tagging.

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Original GitHub repository is accessible at <https://github.com/gayatri-01/POS-Tagging-in-Hindi-Document>.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

No conflict of interest.

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